

Vector Summary

Vector ID	VB201122-1083bzq
Vector Name	pLV[Exp]-Neo-TRE>{Stuffer_300}
Vector Size	8237 bp
Viral Genome Size	4762 bp
Vector Type	Mammalian Gene Expression Lentiviral Vector
Plasmid Copy Number	High
Antibiotic Resistance	Ampicillin
Cloning Host	VB UltraStable (or alternative strain)

Vector Map

Vector Components

Name	Position	Size (bp)	Type	Description	Application notes

Name	Position	Size (bp)	Type	Description	Application notes
RSV promoter	■ 1-229	229	Promoter	Rous sarcoma virus enhancer/promoter	Strong promoter; drives transcription of viral RNA in packaging cells.
Δ5' LTR	■ 230-410	181	LTR	Truncated HIV-1 5' long terminal repeat	Allows transcription of viral RNA and its packaging into virus.
Ψ	■ 521-565	45	Miscellaneous	HIV-1 packaging signal	Allows packaging of viral RNA into virus.
RRE	■ 1075-1308	234	Miscellaneous	HIV-1 Rev response element	Rev protein binding site that allows Rev-dependent nuclear export of viral RNA during viral packaging.
cPPT	■ 1803-1920	118	Miscellaneous	Central polypurine tract	Facilitates the nuclear import of HIV-1 cDNA through a central DNA flap.
TRE	■ 1959-2382	424	Promoter	Tetracycline-responsive element promoter (2nd generation)	Regulated by a class of transcription factors (e.g. tTA, rtTA and tTS) whose activities are dependent on tetracycline or its analogs (e.g. doxycycline).
Stuffer_300	■ 2407-2706	300	CDS		<i>None</i>
WPRE	■ 2745-3342	598	Miscellaneous	Woodchuck hepatitis virus posttranscriptional regulatory element	Enhances virus stability in packaging cells, leading to higher titer of packaged virus; enhances higher expression of transgenes.
mPGK promoter	■ 3361-3871	511	Promoter	Mouse phosphoglycerate kinase 1 promoter	Medium-strength promoter.
Neo	■ 3881-4675	795	CDS	Neomycin resistance gene	Allows cells to be resistant to geneticin (G418).

Name	Position	Size (bp)	Type	Description	Application notes
Δ U3/3' LTR	4757-4991	235	LTR	Truncated HIV-1 3' long terminal repeat	Allows packaging of viral RNA into virus; self-inactivates the 5' LTR by a copying mechanism during viral genome integration; contains polyadenylation signal for transcription termination.
SV40 early pA	5064-5198	135	PolyA_signal	Simian virus 40 early polyadenylation signal	Allows transcription termination and polyadenylation of mRNA transcribed by Pol II RNA polymerase.
Ampicillin	6152-7012	861	CDS	Ampicillin resistance gene	Allows E. coli to be resistant to ampicillin.
pUC ori	7183-7771	589	Rep_origin	pUC origin of replication	Facilitates plasmid replication in E. coli; regulates high-copy plasmid number (500-700).

Note: Components added by user are listed in **bold red** text.

Vector Sequence

```

1  AATGTAGTCT TATGCAATAC TCTTGTAGTC TTGCAACATG GTAACGATGA GTTAGCAACA TGCCTTACAA
71  GGAGAGAAAA AGCACCGTGC ATGCCGATTG GTGGAAGTAA GGTGGTACGA TCGTGCCTTA TTAGGAAGGC
141 AACAGACGGG TCTGACATGG ATTGGACGAA CCACTGAATT GCCGCATTGC AGAGATATTG TATTTAAGTG
211 CCTAGCTCGA TACATAAACG GGTCTCTCTG GTTAGACCAG ATCTGAGCCT GGGAGCTCTC TGGCTAACTA
281 GGGAACCCAC TGCTTAAGCC TCAATAAAGC TTGCCTTGAG TGCTTCAAGT AGTGTGTGCC CGTCTGTTGT
351 GTGACTCTGG TAACTAGAGA TCCCTCAGAC CCTTTTAGTC AGTGTGAAAA ATCTCTAGCA GTGGCGCCCG
421 AACAGGGACT TAAAAGCGAA AGGAAACCA GAGGAGCTCT CTCGACGCAG GACTCGGCTT GCTGAAGCGC
491 GCACGGCAAG AGGCGAGGGG CGGCGACTGG TGAGTACGCC AAAAATTTTG ACTAGCGGAG GCTAGAAGGA
561 GAGAGATGGG TCGGAGAGCG TCAGTATTAA GCGGGGAGA ATTAGATCGC GATGGGAAAA AATTCGGTTA
631 AGGCCAGGGG GAAAGAAAAA ATATAATTA AACATATAG TATGGGCAAG CAGGGAGCTA GAACGATTCCG
701 CAGTTAATCC TGGCCTGTTA GAAACATCAG AAGGCTGTAG ACAAATACTG GGACAGCTAC AACCATCCCT
771 TCAGACAGGA TCAGAAGAAC TTAGATCATT ATATAATACA GTAGCAACCC TCTATTGTGT GCATCAAAGG
841 ATAGAGATAA AAGACACCAA GGAAGCTTTA GACAAGATAG AGGAAGAGCA AAACAAAAGT AAGACCACCG
911 CACAGCAAGC GGCCGCTGAT CTTAGACCTT GGAGGAGGAG ATATGAGGGA CAATTGGAGA AGTGAATTAT
981 ATAAATATAA AGTAGTAAAA ATTGAACCAT TAGGAGTAGC ACCACCAAG GCAAAGAGAA GAGTGGTGCA
1051 GAGAGAAAAA AGAGCAGTGG GAATAGGAGC TTTGTTCTT GGGTCTTGG GAGCAGCAGG AAGCACTATG
1121 GGCGCAGCGT CAATGACGCT GACGGTACAG GCCAGACAAT TATTGTCTGG TATAGTGCAG CAGCAGAACA
1191 ATTTGCTGAG GGCTATTGAG GCGCAACAGC ATCTGTTGCA ACTCACAGTC TGGGCATCA AGCAGCTCCA

```

1261 GGCAAGAATC CTGGCTGTGG AAAGATACCT AAAGGATCAA CAGCTCCTGG GGATTTGGGG TTGCTCTGGA
 1331 AAACTCATTT GCACCACTGC TGTGCCTTGG AATGCTAGTT GGAGTAATAA ATCTCTGGAA CAGATTTGGA
 1401 ATCACACGAC CTGGATGGAG TGGGACAGAG AAATTAACAA TTACACAAGC TTAATACACT CCTTAATTGA
 1471 AGAATCGCAA AACCAGCAAG AAAAGAATGA ACAAGAATTA TTGGAATTAG ATAAATGGGC AAGTTTGTGG
 1541 AATTGGTTTA ACATAACAAA TTGGCTGTGG TATATAAAAT TATTCATAAT GATAGTAGGA GGCTTGGTAG
 1611 GTTTAAGAAT AGTTTTTGCT GTACTTTCTA TAGTGAATAG AGTTAGGCAG GGATATTCAC CATTATCGTT
 1681 TCAGACCCAC CTCCCAACCC CGAGGGGACC CGACAGGCC GAAGGAATAG AAGAAGAAGG TGGAGAGAGA
 1751 GACAGAGACA GATCCATTCG ATTAGTGAAC GGATCTCGAC GGTATCGCTA GCTTTTAAAA GAAAAGGGGG
 1821 GATTGGGGGG TACAGTGCAG GGGAAAGAAT AGTAGACATA ATAGCAACAG ACATACAAAC TAAAGAATTA
 1891 CAAAAACAAA TTACAAAAAT TCAAAATTTT ACTAGTGATT ATCGGATCAA CTTTGTATAG AAAAGTTGGG
 1961 TACCGAGCTC GACTTTCCT TTTCTCTATC ACTGATAGGG AGTGGTAAAC TCGACTTTCA CTTTTCTCTA
 2031 TCACTGATAG GGAGTGGTAA ACTCGACTTT CACTTTTCTC TATCACTGAT AGGGAGTGGT AAACTCGACT
 2101 TTCACTTTTC TCTATCACTG ATAGGGAGTG GTAACCTCGA CTTTCACTTT TCTCTATCAC TGATAGGGAG
 2171 TGGTAAACTC GACTTTCCT TTTCTCTATC ACTGATAGGG AGTGGTAAAC TCGACTTTCA CTTTTCTCTA
 2241 TCACTGATAG GGAGTGGTAA ACTCGACCTA TATAAGCAGA GCTCGTTTAG TGAACCGTCA GATCGCCTGG
 2311 AGACGCCATC CACGCTGTTT TGACCTCCAT AGAAGACACC GGGACCGATC CAGCCTCCGC GGCCCCGAAT
 2381 TGCAAGTTTG TACAAAAAAG CAGGCTGTGC TTTTACAACG TCGTGACTGG GAAAACCCTG GCGTTACCCA
 2451 ACTTAATCGC CTTGCAGCAC ATCCCCCTTT CGCCAGCTGG CGTAATAGCG AAGAGGCCCG CACCGATCGC
 2521 CCTTCCAAC AGTTGCGCAG CCTGAATGGC GAATGCGCT TTGCTGGTT TCCGGCACCA GAAGCGGTGC
 2591 CGGAAAGCTG GCTGGAGTGC GATCTTCTG AGGCCGATC TGTCGTCGTC CCCTCAAAC GGCAGATGCA
 2661 CGGTTACGAT GCGCCCATCT ACACCAACGT AACCTATCCC ATTACGACCC AGCTTTCTTG TACAAAGTGG
 2731 TGATAATCGA ATTCCGATAA TCAACCTCTG GATTACAAAA TTTGTGAAAG ATTGACTGGT ATTCTTAACT
 2801 ATGTTGCTCC TTTTACGCTA TGTGGATACG CTGCTTTAAT GCCTTTGTAT CATGCTATTG CTTCCCCTAT
 2871 GGCTTTCATT TTCTCCTCCT TGTATAAATC CTGGTTGCTG TCTCTTATG AGGAGTTGTG GCCCCGTTGC
 2941 AGGCAACGTG GCGTGGTGTG CACTGTGTTT GCTGACGCAA CCCCACTGG TTGGGGCATT GCCACCACCT
 3011 GTCAGCTCCT TTCCGGGACT TTGCTTTCC CCCTCCCTAT TGCCACGGCG GAACTCATCG CCGCTGCCT
 3081 TGCCCGCTGC TGGACAGGGG CTCGGCTGTT GGGCACTGAC AATTCCGTGG TGTTGTCGGG GAAGCTGACC
 3151 TCCTTCCAT GGCTGCTCGC CTGTGTTGCC ACCTGGATTC TGCGCGGGAC GTCCTTCTGC TACGTCCCTT
 3221 CGGCCCTCAA TCCAGCGGAC CTTCTTCCC GCGGCCTGCT GCCGGCTCTG CGGCCTCTTC CGCGTCTTCC
 3291 CCTTCGCCCT CAGACGAGTC GGATCTCCCT TTGGGCCGCC TCCCCGCATC GGGAATTCCC GCGGTTCCGAA
 3361 TTCTACCGGG TAGGGGAGGC GCTTTTCCA AGGCAGTCTG GAGCATGCGC TTAGCAGCC CCGCTGGGCA
 3431 CTTGCGCTA CACAAGTGGC CTCTGGCCTC GCACACATTC CACATCCACC GGTAGGCGCC AACCGGCTCC
 3501 GTTCTTTGGT GGCCCCTCG CGCCACCTTC TACTCCTCCC CTAGTCAGGA AGTTCCCCCC CGCCCCGACG
 3571 CTCGCGTCGT GCAGGACGTG ACAAATGGAA GTAGCACGTC TCACTAGTCT CGTGCAGATG GACAGACCCG
 3641 CTGAGCAATG GAAGCGGGTA GGCCTTTGGG GCAGCGGCCA ATAGCAGCTT TGCTCCTTCG CTTTCTGGGC
 3711 TCAGAGGCTG GGAAGGGGTG GGTCCGGGGG CGGGCTCAGG GGCGGGCTCA GGGGCGGGGC GGGCGCCCCG
 3781 AGGTCCTCCG GAGGCCCGGC ATTCTGCACG CTTCAAAAGC GCACGTCTGC CGCGCTGTTT TCCTTCTCCT
 3851 CATCTCCGGG CCTTTCGACC TCACGTGCGC ATGATTGAAC AAGATGGATT GCACGCAGGT TCTCCGGCCG
 3921 CTTGGGTGGA GAGGCTATTC GGCTATGACT GGGCACAACA GACAATCGGC TGCTCTGATG CCGCCGTGTT
 3991 CCGGCTGTCA GCGCAGGGGC GCCCAGTTCT TTTTGTCAAG ACCGACCTGT CCGGTGCCTT GAATGAACTG
 4061 CAAGACGAGG CAGCGCGGCT ATCGTGGCTG GCCACGACGG GCGTTCCTTG CGCAGCTGTG CTCGACGTTG
 4131 TCACTGAAGC GGGAAGGGAC TGGCTGCTAT TGGGCGAAGT GCCGGGGCAG GATCTCCTGT CATCTCACCT
 4201 TGCTCCTGCC GAGAAAGTAT CCATCATGGC TGATGCAATG CGGCGGCTGC ATACGCTTGA TCCGGCTACC
 4271 TGCCCATTCG ACCACCAAGC GAAACATCGC ATCGAGCGAG CACGTACTCG GATGGAAGCC GGTCTTGTGC
 4341 ATCAGGATGA TCTGGACGAA GAGCATCAGG GGCTCGCGCC AGCCGAACTG TTCGCCAGGC TCAAGGCGAG
 4411 CATGCCCGAC GGCGAGGATC TCGTCTGAC CCATGGCGAT GCCTGCTTGC CGAATATCAT GGTGGAAAT
 4481 GGCCGCTTTT CTGGATTCAT CGACTGTGGC CGGCTGGGTG TGGCGGACCG CTATCAGGAC ATAGCGTTGG

4551 CTACCCGTGA TATTGCTGAA GAGCTTGGCG GCGAATGGGC TGACCGCTTC CTCGTGCTTT ACGGTATCGC
 4621 CGCTCCCGAT TCGCAGCGCA TCGCCTTCTA TCGCCTTCTT GACGAGTTCT TCTGAGCGGG ACTCTGGGTA
 4691 CCTTTAAGAC CAATGACTTA CAAGGCAGCT GTAGATCTTA GCCACTTTTT AAAAGAAAAG GGGGGACTGG
 4761 AAGGGCTAAT TCACTCCCAA CGAAGACAAG ATCTGCTTTT TGCTTGACT GGGTCTCTCT GGTTAGACCA
 4831 GATCTGAGCC TGGGAGCTCT CTGGCTAACT AGGGAACCCA CTGCTTAAGC CTCAATAAAG CTTGCCTTGA
 4901 GTGCTTCAAG TAGTGTGTGC CCGTCTGTTG TGTGACTCTG GTAAGTAGAG ATCCCTCAGA CCCTTTTAGT
 4971 CAGTGTGGAA AATCTCTAGC AGTAGTAGTT CATGTCATCT TATTATTCAG TATTATAAC TTGCAAAGAA
 5041 ATGAATATCA GAGAGTGAGA GGAACCTGTT TATTGCAGCT TATAATGGTT ACAAATAAAG CAATAGCATC
 5111 ACAAATTTCA CAAATAAAGC ATTTTTTTC A CTGCATTCTA GTTGTGGTTT GTCCAAACTC ATCAATGTAT
 5181 CTTATCATGT CTGGCTCTAG CTATCCC GCC CTAACTCCG CCCATCCCGC CCCTAACTCC GCCCAGTTCC
 5251 GCCCATTCTC CGCCCCATGG CTGACTAATT TTTTTTATTT ATGCAGAGGC CGAGGCCGCC TCGGCCTCTG
 5321 AGCTATTCCA GAAGTAGTGA GGAGGCTTTT TTGGAGGCCT AGGGACGTAC CCAATTCGCC CTATAGTGAG
 5391 TCGTATTACG CGCGCTCACT GGCCGTCGTT TTACAACGTC GTGACTGGGA AAACCCTGGC GTTACCCAAC
 5461 TTAATCGCCT TGCAGCACAT CCCCCTTTCG CCAGCTGGCG TAATAGCGAA GAGGCCCGCA CCGATCGCCC
 5531 TTCCAACAG TTGCGCAGCC TGAATGGCGA ATGGGACGCG CCCTGTAGCG GCGCATTAAAG CGCGCGGGT
 5601 GTGGTGTTA CGCGCAGCGT GACCGCTACA CTTGCCAGCG CCCTAGCGCC CGCTCCTTTC GCTTCTTCC
 5671 CTTCTTTCT CGCCACGTTT GCCGGCTTTC CCCGTCAAGC TCTAAATCGG GGGCTCCCTT TAGGGTCCG
 5741 ATTTAGTGCT TTACGGCACC TCGACCCCAA AAACTTGAT TAGGGTGATG GTTCACGTAG TGGGCCATCG
 5811 CCCTGATAGA CGTTTTTTCG CCCTTTGACG TTGGAGTCCA CGTTCTTTAA TAGTGACTC TTGTTCCAAA
 5881 CTGGAACAAC ACTCAACCT ATCTCGGTCT ATTCTTTTGA TTTATAAGG ATTTTGCCGA TTTCCGGCCTA
 5951 TTGGTAAAA AATGAGCTGA TTTAACAAAA ATTTAACGCG AATTTAACA AAATATTAAC GCTTACAATT
 6021 TAGGTGGCAC TTTTCGGGGA AATGTGCGCG GAACCCCTAT TTGTTTATTT TTCTAAATAC ATTCAAATAT
 6091 GTATCCGCTC ATGAGACAAT AACCTGATA AATGCTTCAA TAATATTGAA AAAGGAAGAG TATGAGTATT
 6161 CAACATTTCC GTGTGCCCC TATTCCCTTT TTTGCGGCAT TTTGCCTTCC TGTTTTTGCT CACCCAGAAA
 6231 CGCTGGTGAA AGTAAAAGAT GCTGAAGATC AGTTGGGTGC ACGAGTGGGT TACATCGAAC TGATCTCAA
 6301 CAGCGGTAAG ATCCTTGAGA GTTTTCGCC CGAAGAACGT TTTCCAATGA TGAGCACTTT TAAAGTTCTG
 6371 CTATGTGGCG CGGTATTATC CCGTATTGAC GCCGGGCAAG AGCAACTCGG TCGCCGCATA CACTATTCTC
 6441 AGAATGACTT GGTTGAGTAC TCACCAGTCA CAGAAAAGCA TCTTACGGAT GGCATGACAG TAAGAGAATT
 6511 ATGCAGTGCT GCCATAACCA TGAGTGATAA CACTGCGGCC AACTTACTTC TGACAACGAT CGGAGGACCG
 6581 AAGGAGCTAA CCGCTTTTTT GCACAACATG GGGGATCATG TAACTCGCCT TGATCGTTGG GAACCGGAGC
 6651 TGAATGAAGC CATAACAAAC GACGAGCGTG ACACCACGAT GCCTGTAGCA ATGGCAACAA CGTTGCGCAA
 6721 ACTATTAAC TGGCAACTAC TTAATCTAGC TTCCGGCAA CAATTAATAG ACTGGATGGA GGCAGATAAA
 6791 GTTGCAGGAC CACTTCTGCG CTCGGCCCTT CCGGCTGGCT GGTTTATTGC TGATAAATCT GGAGCCGGTG
 6861 AGCGTGGGTC TCGCGGTATC ATTGCAGCAC TGGGGCCAGA TGTAAGCCC TCCCGTATCG TAGTTATCTA
 6931 CACGACGGGG AGTCAGGCAA CTATGGATGA ACGAAATAGA CAGATCGCTG AGATAGGTGC CTCACTGATT
 7001 AAGCATTGGT AACTGTCAGA CCAAGTTTAC TCATATATAC TTTAGATTGA TTTAAAACCT CATTTTTAA
 7071 TTAAAAGGAT CTAGGTGAAG ATCCTTTTTG ATAATCTCAT GACCAAATC CCTAACGTG AGTTTTTCGT
 7141 CCACTGAGCG TCAGACCCCG TAGAAAAGAT CAAAGGATCT TCTTGAGATC CTTTTTTTCT GCGCGTAATC
 7211 TGCTGCTTGC AAACAAAAAA ACCACCGCTA CCAGCGGTGG TTTGTTTGCC GGATCAAGAG CTACCAACTC
 7281 TTTTTCCGAA GGTAACCTGGC TTCAGCAGAG CGCAGATACC AAATACTGTT CTCTAGTGT AGCCGTAGTT
 7351 AGGCCACCAC TTCAAGAACT CTGTAGCACC GCCTACATAC CTCGCTCTGC TAATCCTGTT ACCAGTGGCT
 7421 GCTGCCAGTG GCGATAAGTC GTGTCTTACC GGGTTGGACT CAAGACGATA GTTACCGGAT AAGGCGCAGC
 7491 GGTCGGGCTG AACGGGGGGT TCGTGCACAC AGCCAGCTT GGAGCGAACG ACCTACACCG AACTGAGATA
 7561 CCTACAGCGT GAGCTATGAG AAAGCGCCAC GCTTCCCGAA GAGAGAAAAG CGGACAGGTA TCCGGTAAGC
 7631 GGCAGGGTCG GAACAGGAGA GCGCACGAGG GAGCTTCCAG GGGGAAACGC CTGGTATCTT TATAGTCTGT
 7701 TCGGGTTTTCG CCACCTCTGA CTTGAGCGTC GATTTTTGTG ATGCTCGTCA GGGGGGCGGA GCCTATGGAA
 7771 AAACGCCAGC AACCGGCCT TTTTACGGTT CCTGGCCTTT TGCTGGCCTT TTGCTCACAT GTTCTTTCCT
 GCGTTATCCC CTGATTCTGT GGATAACCGT ATTACCGCT TTGAGTGAGC TGATAACCGCT CGCCGACGCC

7841 GAACGACCGA GCGCAGCGAG TCAGTGAGCG AGGAAGCGGA AGAGCGCCA ATACGCAAAC CGCCTCTCCC
 7911 CGCGCGTTGG CCGATTCATT AATGCAGCTG GCACGACAGG TTTCCCGACT GGAAAGCGGG CAGTGAGCGC
 7981 AACGCAATTA ATGTGAGTTA GCTCACTCAT TAGGCACCCC AGGCTTTACA CTTTATGCTT CCGGCTCGTA
 8051 TGTTGTGTGG AATTGTGAGC GGATAACAAT TTCACACAGG AACAGCTAT GACCATGATT ACGCCAAGCG
 8121 CGCAATTAAC CCTCACTAAA GGGAACAAAA GCTGGAGCTG CAAGCTT
 8191

Validation by Restriction Enzyme Digestion

Restriction Enzymes	Cutting Sites	DNA Fragments (bp)
AgeI	[3479]	[8237]
ApaI	[2959, 6268, 7514]	[3309, 1246, 3682]
AflII	[294, 4875]	[4581, 3656]
AvrII	[5359]	[8237]
DraIII	[5800]	[8237]
ApaI+AgeI	[2959, 3479, 6268, 7514]	[520, 2789, 1246, 3682]
ApaI+AvrII	[2959, 5359, 6268, 7514]	[2400, 909, 1246, 3682]
ApaI+AflII	[294, 2959, 4875, 6268, 7514]	[2665, 1916, 1393, 1246, 1017]
ApaI+DraIII	[2959, 5800, 6268, 7514]	[2841, 468, 1246, 3682]